

ISic0922

I.Sicily inscription 0922

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 57

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κῆτε
2. Ἐλπίς ἢ παρθέ
3. νος ἐκβένον
4. τος μη(νός) Ἀπρι(λίου)
5. τῆς λ

Apparatus

Text of IG XIV

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492552

EDCS 39102079

PHI 140403

Bibliography

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Agnello, S.L. 1953. *Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia.* Rome. At no.3

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0922. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340078>